

Unintended Solidarity and Resistance in Prisons and Their Legacy After 1989

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Introduction

The political prisoners of the late 1940s and early 1950s were a heterogeneous group, encompassing a wide range of political and religious beliefs, social classes and cultural backgrounds. The repression of the communist dictatorship affected former participants in domestic and foreign resistance, as well as Catholic intellectuals, evangelical clergymen, scouts, students, and rural peasants who rejected collectivization. The common denominator of their fates was the experience of imprisonment, which brought them into the environment of a “total institution” (Goffman) in which they faced not only physical and psychological violence, but also profound social isolation and stigmatization.

The aim of this study is to interpret the prison experience not only as an act of repressive politics of the communist regime, but also as a process of collective identity formation, solidarity and, consequently, political activism. Attention is paid to how this experience became part of memory politics after 1989 and how the victimhood of the victims of political persecution was constructed. I understand the victimhood as social construct and a source of political and moral capital. In the Czech case, there was a specific transformation of the victim into a “heroic victim”, i.e. into a person who not only suffered but actively resisted. I refer to this phenomenon as *heroic victimhood*.

The experience of political prisoners in the 1950s can be analysed on two levels. The first relates to the everyday reality of prison life, shaped by harsh conditions, physical and psychological pressure and strict control. The second level involves the process of prisoners adapting to their new environment, developing survival strategies and finding ways to preserve their human dignity. These mechanisms led not only to the formation of strong interpersonal bonds, but also to the gradual creation of an “us versus them” dichotomy – prisoners versus guards and the repressive regime.

After November 1989, former political prisoners entered the public space as one of the most morally respected groups. Their experience was framed not only as one of victimhood, but above all in the category of active resistance: as “the first to resist the communist dictatorship”. This reinterpretation of their own identity was a key element of self-representation and political agency, enabling ex-prisoners to transform trauma into a form of moral authority.

The prison experience in the 1950s

Following February 1948, the Czechoslovak prison system became the primary tool for political repression. In a relatively brief period, it underwent a profound metamorphosis in

accordance with Soviet principles: an emphasis on “re-education” through forced labour, centralisation of administration and militarisation of the supervisory apparatus. In the prisons and labour camps, real or perceived opponents were not only punished but also used as cheap labour to build heavy industry.

Every aspect of prisoners’ lives was subjected to detailed regulation and permanent surveillance. The most famous prisons, symbolizing political repression, were Plzeň-Bory, Mírov, Valdice, Leopoldov, including the women’s prisons in Želiezovce and Pardubice. Common features were brutal treatment, poor nutrition, harsh labour standards and the omnipresent threat of punishment. The guards, often poorly educated and ideologically indoctrinated, combined physical violence with psychological coercion. Prison life meant profound deprivation: prisoners were cut off from family and friends, lost the opportunity to perform traditional gender roles, and were reduced to a labour force. Yet it was this extreme situation that allowed for the emergence of specific subcultures, hierarchies and unwritten rules of survival. In their memoirs, prisoners often recall following an unwritten code: not to cooperate with the regime, not to denounce others.

From a theoretical perspective, the prison experience can be understood as identity formation under conditions of cultural trauma and as a process in which collective memory is created and transformed through shared narratives of survival. Mechanisms of survival, solidarity and resistance became the basis for the later construction of “us versus them” and for prisoners’ narrative memory.

Solidarity and resistance behind bars

One of the paradoxical consequences of communist repression was that the environment of prisons and camps, designed to break down individuality, became a site for the formation of strong bonds, survival strategies and collective identity. Solidarity was not absolute; in all total institutions there were individuals who collaborated with guards or denounced fellow prisoners. These, if recognized, were stigmatized and isolated.

A sharp moral code emerged: silence and mutual aid were the norm, while collaboration with the repressive apparatus meant exclusion. This contrast of solidarity and betrayal fundamentally influenced the later memory construction of the prison experience. Memories often idealised solidarity and demonised the denouncer, reinforcing the polarised division of the world and helping to create a collective identity that was maintained even after release.

From a *memory studies* perspective, these processes can be understood as the formation of cultural memory, where shared experiences of suffering and resistance create a collective framework for interpreting the past. Solidarity became not only a survival tool but also a moral category.

The memory grasp of experience

Political prisoners’ memories of the 1950s often emphasise solidarity and collective resilience. In narrative memory, the prison transformed from a period of suffering into a period when a “brotherhood of political prisoners” was emerging. In memoirs, oral histories

activities in the Confederation, the motif of a “golden age of friendship behind bars” emerges, when prisoners supported each other and learned to rely on each other. However, this interpretation is idealised; the reality was often more complex, involving conflict, denunciation and psychological breakdown.

The experience of solidarity and betrayal led to the gradual formation of a clear image of “us” versus “them”. The “we” represented prisoners defined by a shared experience of suffering, a belief in justice and mutual support. “They” then embodied the regime, the guards and informers, in other words, they represented oppression and evil. This dichotomous view enabled survival under extreme conditions and became part of the prisoners’ identity even after their release, which had a lasting impact on their political and symbolic role after 1989.

Memory and self-representation after 1989

After 1989, the prison experience became part of the public discourse. Political changes allowed prisoners to articulate their own stories and transform them into a tool for collective self-representation. The idealization of solidarity and friendship dominated, which had a mobilizing potential and placed prisoners in the role of heroes. At the same time, however, it led to a homogenization of memory that suppressed conflicts and contradictory experiences.

The Confederation of Political Prisoners (KPV), founded in December 1989, played an important role. Already in 1990 it had around 16,000 members and more than 80 branches. The Confederation sought both rehabilitation, social security and health care, and a significant voice in shaping a new political culture and memory policy. The association’s activities had not only a political but also a strongly therapeutic dimension: the gathering of political prisoners and their families offered a space for sharing traumas and memories and for consolidating collective identity.

However, this process was not without its problems. Emphasising heroism and solidarity marginalised dissenting voices, such as those who recalled conflict, disappointment or their own failures. Collective memory thus became a tool for legitimation rather than open dialogue. As the development of the Confederation shows, the emphasis on “moral purity” and exclusivity gradually led to the exclusion of some members who were suspected of collaborating with the State Security. While this process reinforced the image of the political prisoner as an absolutely pure and heroic figure, it also contributed to polarization and conflict within the organization itself.

The politics of memory and the “third” anti-communist resistance

After 1989, political prisoners sought to be perceived not as passive victims but as active fighters against communism. The discourse of the “third resistance” was based on a historical tradition: the first resistance for the creation of Czechoslovakia, the second resistance against Nazism. The political prisoners sought to make their struggle against the communist dictatorship a “third resistance”, a continuation of the national liberation tradition that was supposed to legitimise their role in society. The Confederation’s founding documents demanded that the prison experience be understood as a direct expression of resistance to

communism. This discourse reinforced prisoners' moral claim to recognition and symbolically elevated them above the common categories of "victims."

Legislative recognition of anti-communist resistance in the form demanded by Confederation leaders was unfeasible in the early 1990s because there was neither political nor social consensus over the existence of this resistance. In the following years, however, Confederation leaders exerted pressure through memoranda, commemorations and political lobbying. Contacts with conservative right-wing parties, especially the Civic Democratic Party and the KDU-CSL, which shared an anti-communist discourse and readily used the symbolism of the anticommunist resistance in their political struggle against the left, played an important role.

After more than twenty years of efforts, Act No. 262/2011 Coll., on Participants in the Resistance and Resistance against Communism, was adopted in 2011. This law enshrined the concept of the "Third Resistance" and made it possible to issue certificates of participation. The approval of the law was a victory for the KPV, but practice has also shown problematic aspects – complicated administrative procedures and exclusivity, which led to a new division between "fighters" and "victims". The debate on the Third Resistance reflected a broader dispute over the interpretation of history: between "memory from below" (prisoners and their associations) and "memory from above" (the state, academic institutions). The Czech case is specific in comparison with Germany: while there the victims of the SED-dictatorship sought rather economic compensation, in the Czech Republic the discourse of "fighters" dominated.

In terms of *transitional justice*, the Czech case is an example of symbolic justice: the prisoners received legislative and symbolic recognition, which strengthened their moral authority, but at the same time did not address all the issues of trauma, collaboration or transgenerational impact.

The transformation of the victimhood

The victimhood began to take shape during imprisonment and was gradually consolidated after release and after 1989. Whereas before 1989 victimhood was formed in isolation in a family and friendship context, after 1989 it was influenced by political and social conditions. The adoption of the heroic role made it possible to reinterpret suffering as evidence of bravery and meaningful sacrifice. Collective memory and associational activity further reinforced this interpretation and provided legitimacy for social claims and political demands. The transformation of the prisoner's identity involved not only a narrative of heroic sacrifice, but also moral and symbolic authority that was used in public discourse and memory politics.

Conclusion

Political imprisonment in the 1950s was not just an episode of the repressive policies of the communist dictatorship, but became an important source of solidarity, collective identity and moral authority. Repression aimed at breaking individuals paradoxically contributed to the formation of an actor that played a key role in shaping memory politics after 1989. The political prisoner established himself not only as a symbol of suffering, but more importantly of resistance and moral authority.

Through the activities of the Confederation of Political Prisoners, the legislative recognition of the so-called “Third Resistance” was promoted and the image of political prisoners as the first and legitimate opponents of the communist regime was consolidated. This process, however, exhibits ambivalences: the homogenization of memory has marginalized alternative experiences and reproduced new forms of symbolic exclusion, posing a challenge for historical research. Analytical-historical approaches that critically reflect the dominant discourse have continued to face criticism not only from former political prisoners, whose voice is now diluted by old age and internal conflicts within the Confederation (especially since 2015), but also from some historians who have worked closely with the organization in the past.

As a result, the research space is limited: there is a lack of systematic psychohistorical studies of trauma and its transgenerational transmission, the collaboration of some prisoners with the State Security and a deeper analysis of their motivations and survival strategies. The current state of research thus reflects the tension between symbolic recognition, moral authority and the actual complex experiences of political prisoners.

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